

1 **APOC1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the apolipoprotein C1, APOC1, was among those whose
14 expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total transcription between
15 tumor and normal brain tissue. APOC1 expression levels were significantly increased in glioblastoma
16 tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. APOC1 function at the systems level was assessed by
17 studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed brain. APOC1 is a target of
18 interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed chemotherapeutic regimen that
19 utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and healthy non-transformed tissues to maximize
20 efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

21
22
23
24
25
26 Keywords: APOC1, apolipoprotein C1, glioblastoma, systems biology of glioblastoma, targeted
27 therapeutics in glioblastoma.
28

Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole transcriptome methods.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional co-regulation studies (8).

Results

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6) to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

APOC1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1789007	1.05E-09	-7.8329345	12.071294	-2.23282791	APOC1	997/47,229	97.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of apolipoprotein C1, encoded by APOC1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of APOC1 changed more than 95% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the APOC1 fold-change indicating increased quantity of APOC1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of APOC1 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

$n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	Gene	Rank	%DE
341	8.09E-05	0.535	-3.9416061	-2.11055841	APOC1	1530/19,678	92.2

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of APOC1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of APOC1 here changed more than 90% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of APOC1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of APOC1 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

Thus, APOC1 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the glioblastoma subtype in humans.

APOC1 transcriptional co-regulation.

Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

In the transformed brain, APOC1 was transcriptionally co-regulated with complement components C1QA, C1QB, and C1QC.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 APOC1 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
3 into APOC1 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its
4 co-regulation with APOC1 .

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 apolipoprotein C1, APOC1, was among the genes most differentially expressed in the
7 primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; APOC1 was expressed at significantly higher levels in
8 glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. APOC1 is a target of interest for rationally designed
9 medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Alexander, B.M. and Cloughesy, T.F., 2017. Adult glioblastoma. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 35(21), pp.2402-2409.
2. Liu, A.Y., 2000. Differential expression of cell surface molecules in prostate cancer cells. *Cancer research*, 60(13), pp.3429-3434.
3. Singer, S., Socci, N.D., Ambrosini, G., Sambol, E., Decarolis, P., Wu, Y., O'Connor, R., Maki, R., Viale, A., Sander, C. and Schwartz, G.K., 2007. Gene expression profiling of liposarcoma identifies distinct biological types/subtypes and potential therapeutic targets in well-differentiated and dedifferentiated liposarcoma. *Cancer research*, 67(14), pp.6626-6636.
4. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
5. Kruthika, B.S., Jain, R., Arivazhagan, A., Bharath, R.D., Yasha, T.C., Kondaiah, P. and Santosh, V., 2019. Transcriptome profiling reveals PDZ binding kinase as a novel biomarker in peritumoral brain zone of glioblastoma. *Journal of neuro-oncology*, 141, pp.315-325.
6. GSE184643. Xiong Jin. Henan University, School of Pharmacy. Henan Key Laboratory of Brain Targeted Bio-nanomedicine. China.
7. Omuro, A. and DeAngelis, L.M., 2013. Glioblastoma and other malignant gliomas: a clinical review. *Jama*, 310(17), pp.1842-1850.
8. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.